

Exploring Identification of Social Determinants of Health (SDOH) Data in NHLBI BioData Catalyst® (BDC) Using Embedding-Based Methods

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Abstract:

In alignment with the Make America Healthy Again initiative to promote the policies to improve public health, this initiative focuses on the identification of survey questions and answers in datasets hosted within the NHLBI BioData Catalyst® (BDC) ecosystem for the purpose of easier search in the ecosystem's cohort-building tool, *BDC Powered by PIC-SURE (BDC-PIC-SURE)*. Leveraging data standards developed by the Gravity Project, we systematically evaluated and ranked 113 high-value datasets within BDC based on the variables represented in the Gravity Project domains. The four datasets with the highest representation of variables in the Gravity Project domains were then manually annotated using Simple Knowledge Organization System (SKOS) relations to match survey questions and answers with the Gravity Project elements. We used this manually annotated data set as a "gold standard" to test a proof-of-concept annotation tool that uses embedding-based approaches to match survey-based data with the Gravity Project value set. Performance varied by domain, with employment status being the best (F1-Score = 1.0) and financial insecurity being the worst (F1-Score = 0.42). Some domains, such as financial insecurity, material hardship, and medical cost burden had significant overlap and were challenging for human annotators to differentiate. Future work includes further refinement of this workflow by comparing the performance of different embedding algorithms, examining performance on categorical variables versus continuous variables, determining binning for semantic similarity scores (high, medium, low), and exploring the possibility of other vocabularies or annotating data with multiple domains.

Keywords: HL-7, Gravity Project, biomedical data, embedding models, survey data

Introduction:

Social Determinants of Health (SDOH) encompass a wide range of non-medical factors—such as education and employment—that significantly influence health outcomes¹. Research has consistently demonstrated that challenges such as financial insecurity, food insecurity, and lack of social support contribute to adverse health outcomes, including chronic diseases and mental health conditions.² The impact of these factors directly affects American people, especially young children as identified in the [Make America Healthy Again Initiative](#). Understanding these effects can provide valuable insight into efficient disease prevention efforts and enable effective interventions.

Despite their recognized importance, integrating SDOH data into biomedical research remains complex and fragmented. Traditional biomedical research has focused predominantly on genetic and clinical factors, often overlooking the other dimensions that influence health. SDOH data are frequently collected in multiple ways, such as surveys and social assessments, and often lack standardization in terminologies or coding systems. These challenges hinder seamless integration of SDOH data into structured clinical data systems. Aligning with the national effort of

Make America Healthy again, our research focuses on developing scalable methods to incorporate SDOH data into biomedical research. To address these complexities, initiatives like the Gravity Project³, supported by the Office of the National Coordinator for Health IT (ONC), have developed standardized SDOH data elements using the Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR) framework.⁴ These efforts aim to establish consistent and interoperable methods for recording and sharing SDOH data across health systems. However, widespread adoption is hindered by the need for efficient and scalable methods for mapping and annotating SDOH data across datasets.

This research proposes a novel, scalable approach to annotating and mapping SDOH data within the National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute (NHLBI) BioData Catalyst[®] (BDC) ecosystem⁵, a large-scale research data repository hosting clinical, genomic, and epidemiological datasets. By leveraging embedding-based methods with large language models (LLMs)⁶, this project aims to automate and enhance the mapping of variables to the Gravity Project's standardized domains.⁷ Embedding-based methods have the potential to capture semantic relationships between terms, reducing reliance on manual annotation and enabling more consistent identification and thus leveraging of SDOH data.

The core objectives of this research are as follows:

1. **SDOH Variable Mapping:** To systematically identify and annotate variables in BDC-hosted datasets with standardized Gravity Project domains, leveraging semantic frameworks like SKOS for improved consistency and interoperability.
2. **Embedding-Assisted Annotation:** To explore and implement embedding-based methods that enhance and accelerate the mapping of data, reducing the need for extensive manual annotation while maintaining human oversight for accuracy.
3. **Scalable Proof of Concept:** To validate the scalability and real-world applicability of embedding-based annotation methods, demonstrating their impact on improving the searchability and discoverability of data in large biomedical datasets.

This paper describes the process of annotating SDOH data, applying embedding-based methods, and evaluating the performance of these methods against manually annotated ground truth. By providing a scalable and reproducible approach to integrating SDOH data, we aim to enhance the capacity of researchers to explore and analyze these additional factors that influence health outcomes, ultimately contributing to more comprehensive health research.

Recent studies have explored the potential of machine learning and prompt-based LLM approaches for data annotation. For example, Ralevski et al.⁸ and Yu et al.⁹ have demonstrated the effectiveness of LLMs in extracting and aligning clinical data to standard terminologies. While Lybarger et al.¹⁰ and Guevara et al.¹¹ have used neural network models and fine-tuning methods to map clinical data, their work does not address the inherent challenges of domain diversity and the complex, often subjective nature of SDOH data. In summary, while previous studies have made progress in data annotation and mapping, our work distinguishes itself by addressing the unique challenges of integrating SDOH data into large-scale biomedical research. We leverage embedding techniques to ensure semantic precision and scalability across diverse datasets.

Data:

This research employs data elements with well-defined variables (IDs), detailed descriptions (questions), response options (values), and standardized formats. These elements ensure consistent data collection and facilitate seamless integration across various platforms. Two primary data sources were leveraged in this study:

1. The Gravity Project SDOH Domains

The Gravity Project is a national initiative led by the Office of the National Coordinator for Health IT (ONC), focused on standardizing the collection and sharing of SDOH data¹². As part of this initiative, the Gravity Project has developed terminologies and data standards based on the Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR) framework to enable consistent capture and exchange of SDOH information.⁷ The project's Terminology Workstream defines standardized value sets for 22 SDOH domains, such as financial insecurity, food insecurity, housing instability, educational attainment, social connection, health insurance coverage status, etc.

These value sets provide structured terminology and coding guidelines essential for interoperable data exchange in healthcare systems and research platforms. The Gravity Project's domains served as the target reference for mapping and annotation in this study.

The dataset from the Gravity Project was systematically extracted from its public documentation available on Confluence¹³. The extracted data included standardized domain names, variable names and definitions, and associated values, forming the basis for our annotation and alignment processes.

2. NHLBI BioData Catalyst[®] (BDC)

NHLBI BioData Catalyst[®](BDC), is a cloud-based ecosystem that offers researchers data, analytic tools, applications and workflows in secure workspaces. Researchers can find, access, share, store and compute on hosted data or data they bring to it and utilize this data repository to share scientific data from NHLBI-funded research, so they and others can reproduce findings and reuse data to advance science. *BioData Catalyst Powered by PIC-SURE* (Patient Information Commons Standard Unification of Research Elements) allows researchers to explore studies funded by NHLBI and allows users to create analysis-ready data frames without manually mapping and merging files.

For this research, we focused on datasets accessible through *BDC-PIC-SURE*, which integrates genetic, exposure, imaging, behavioral, and clinical information from multiple sources at the individual patient level. The evaluation encompassed 178,068 unique variables, of which 95,969 had categorical values. For this phase of the analysis, only categorical data was considered.

Methodology:

Our methodology employs two distinct approaches for annotating BDC-hosted datasets based on Gravity Project standards. The manual approach involved expert review and categorization of questions, identifying exact, close, and related matches across key domains. In parallel, an embedding-based approach was used to map thousands of question-response pairs by generating semantic representations and conducting similarity comparisons.

Manual Annotation:

The BDC Data Management Core identified a total of 113 high-value datasets hosted within BDC. Each dataset was manually reviewed for the existence of questions and responses

related to the Gravity Project. The datasets were ranked based on the number of the Gravity Domains represented in each dataset (Table 1). We then selected the top four studies for manual SKOS¹⁵ annotation (Table 2).

Table 1: Number of Gravity Project SDOH domains represented in four BDC-hosted cohorts

StudyName	GRAVITY SDOH DOMAINS														Total Number of Domains							
	Food Insecurity	Housing Instability	Homelessness	Inadequate Housing	Transportation Insecurity	Financial Insecurity	Material Hardship	Employment Status	Educational Attainment	Veteran Status	Stress	Social Connection	Intimate Partner Violence	Elder Abuse		Health Literacy	Health Insurance Coverage Status	Medical Cost Burden	Digital Literacy	Digital Access	Utility Insecurity	
Coronary Artery Risk Development in Young Adults (CARDIA) Study - Cohort	X	X		X		X	X	X	X			X				X	X					10
Hispanic Community Health Study /Study of Latinos (HCHS/SOL)				X		X		X	X	X	X					X	X					9
Women's Health Initiative Clinical Trial and Observational Study						X	X	X	X	X						X	X		X			8
Multi-Ethnic Study of Atherosclerosis (MESA) Cohort	X					X	X	X	X			X				X						7

The four datasets (Table 1) contained 233 questions and their respective responses. These were evaluated manually to assess alignment with data elements in The Gravity Project. Only one question and its response choices from the Financial Insecurity domain had an exact match to a question in The Gravity Project. The majority of the questions and their responses were categorized as a *Related Match* or *Close Match*. The domain category containing the highest number of SKOS match relationships was *Social Connection*, followed by *Health Insurance Coverage Status* and *Educational Attainment*.

Table 2 : Number of Questions and Responses by SKOS Relation in Four Manually-Annotated BDC-Hosted Datasets

SDOH Domain	Match -SKOS Category						Total
	CloseMatch	Narrow Match	Related Match	Broad Match	No Match	Exact Match	
Educational Attainment	24				2		26
Employment Status	4		9		1		14
Health Insurance Coverage Status	17		38				55
Medical Cost Burden		6	12	3			21
Social Connection	13	8	50	3	1		74
Stress			5				5
Veteran Status	2		1				3
Food Insecurity			9				9
Housing Instability			4				4
Inadequate Housing			1				1
Transporation Insecurity			1				1
Financial Insecurity			6		9	1	16
Material Hardship			1		1		2
	1						1
Grand Total	61	14	137	6	14	1	233

Embedding-Based Approach:

The complexity and volume of questions in BDC, coupled with the intricate task of mapping these questions to meaningful domains, necessitated an automated approach capable of capturing nuanced human language. This approach also needed to be scalable, reproducible, and precise to ensure consistent interpretation and alignment of variables and data elements across all BDC datasets. To meet these requirements, we adopted an embedding-based methodology, which offers the following advantages:

- **Reproducibility:** Standardized mappings using interoperable frameworks.
- **Scalability:** Efficient comparison and matching across extensive datasets.
- **Accessibility:** Enhanced querying capabilities for variables across studies with semantic precision.

Preprocessing and Embedding Generation

We transformed $\{question+response\}$ pairs into continuous vector representations (embeddings) to encapsulate the semantic meaning of the combined text. This approach enables sophisticated comparisons, overcoming limitations of simple keyword matching by accounting for variations in wording, synonyms, and context.

To facilitate the mapping process, we created a single embedding for each $\{question+response\}$ pair. Each question (variable description) and its associated responses (values) were combined into a single string, preprocessed, and converted into an embedding using an existing model. We tested two models, the open-source SentenceTransformer model ([all-MiniLM-L6-v2](#))¹⁶ and the OpenAI embedding model ([text-embedding-3-small](#)).

Similarity Comparisons and Metrics

Once converted into embeddings, these representations were stored as vectors. Similarity comparisons were conducted using **cosine similarity**, which quantifies the semantic alignment

between two text vectors by measuring the angle between them. Cosine similarity values range from 0 to 1, with higher values indicating greater semantic alignment. The top match, determined by the highest similarity score, was considered for each comparison. This approach allowed for a more nuanced understanding of text relationships, enabling comparisons that captured subtle differences in phrasing or vocabulary.

Embedding Sets and Mapping Workflow

Two distinct sets of embeddings were generated to enable comprehensive mapping:

1. **Gravity Project Data Elements:** These embeddings represent predefined *{question-response}* pairs from the Gravity Project. They served as the target set for annotating and comparing study variables from BDC, where each variable is represented as a *{question-response}* pair in a variable-to-variable matching exercise.
2. **BDC-Hosted Study Variables:** This set consisted of 83,639 out of 95,969 categorical variables sourced from the BDC data dictionary, exported from *BDC-PIC-SURE* on August 23, 2024. Variables with exceptionally large value sets (some containing more than 200 response options) were excluded. To maintain manageable and relevant data, a cutoff of 10 was applied, meaning only variables with 10 or fewer response options were included in the study. The remaining variables were embedded and compared to the Gravity Project domains for annotation.

For each {Q&A}-{Gravity Data Element} pair, a similarity score ranging from 0 to 1 was computed. This score quantifies the semantic alignment, with values closer to 1 indicating a stronger match (Table 3). It took approximately 3 hours to run 80K+ BDC variables and get specific Gravity Project domain annotations done.

Table 3: Semantic Similarity Score for Three Examples

Example	Source	Question/Variable	Answer/Values	Similarity Score
1	BDC/PIC-SURE	HOW OFTEN DO YOU FEEL THAT YOU LACK COMPANIONSHIP?	HARDLY EVER, OFTEN, SOME OF THE TIME	0.92
	Gravity SDoH Domain: <i>Social Connection</i>	How often do you feel that you lack companionship?	Never, Rarely, Sometimes, Usually, Always	
2	BDC/PIC-SURE	Are you currently living in transitional housing, staying in a shelter, or experiencing homelessness?	No	0.7
	Gravity SDoH Domain: <i>Homelessness</i>	Are you homeless? Or worried that you might be in the future?	Yes, No	
3	BDC/PIC-SURE	TYPE OF CHEST DISCOMFORT	DULL, OTHER, PRESSURE, HEAVY, VISE, SHARP	0.38
	Gravity SDoH Domain: <i>Stress</i>	Have you been under or felt you were under any strain, stress, or pressure? (DURING THE PAST MONTH)	Yes -- almost more than I could bear or stand Yes -- quite a bit of pressure Yes -- some - more than usual Yes -- some - but about usual Yes - a little Not at all	

Similarity Score Visualization

To summarize the distribution of similarity scores, a heat map was generated (Figure 1). The visualization provided the following insights:

- **Similarity Score Binning:** Similarity scores were categorized into three bins (Low: 0-0.3, Medium: 0.3-0.7, High: 0.7-1.0). These bins offered an intuitive overview of semantic alignment across domains. Although heuristic, these boundaries may benefit from further experimental validation or tuning.
- **Domain-Specific Patterns:** Certain domains, such as *Stress*, exhibited a concentration of variables with high similarity scores, indicating strong semantic matches.

- Quantitative Insights:** The heat map detailed the count of variables (varId) in each similarity bin for every SDOH domain, offering a granular view of the mapping distribution.

Figure 1: Heatmap of BDC Variable Distribution Across Gravity Project Domains and Similarity Scores. This heatmap visualizes the distribution of BDC variables (question and response pairs) across domains, with an emphasis on their semantic similarity scores. The 80,000+ data points refer to variables from BDC, which are mapped across various Gravity Project domains. Each domain contains a subset of these variables, and for each BDC variable, the top match is identified based on semantic similarity to the closest domain. These domain names and their corresponding similarity scores are plotted on the heatmap. The Gravity domain associated with the most BDC variables was Social Connections (dark blue) and the domain associated with the fewest variables was Housing Instability (light yellow). The majority of the comparisons received a medium score on semantic similarity. Only 221 comparisons (out of 83,639) received a high score on semantic similarity. The precise thresholds defining scores as low (<0.3), medium (>=0.3, <0.7), or high (>=0.7) similarity will be re-examined in future work.

Evaluation

We evaluated the alignment between manual annotations and the embedding-based approach by assessing the agreement between human-assigned thematic groupings and classifications derived from two embedding models. Specifically, we aimed to determine how well the Gravity domain (thematic grouping) assigned by human experts matched the domain classifications assigned by the embedding-based approach.

To conduct this evaluation, we used a dataset comprising **150 BDC variables manually annotated** with the Gravity domain. The manual annotations served as the ground truth for comparison against the outputs of two embedding models: an open-source **SentenceTransformer model (all-MiniLM-L6-v2)** and the **OpenAI embedding model (text-embedding-3-small)**.

We assessed model performance using standard classification metrics, including:

- **Accuracy:** The overall correctness of predictions.
- **Precision and Recall:** Measures of false positives and false negatives for each class.
- **F1-Score:** A balanced measure that combines precision and recall.
- **Macro and Weighted Averages:** To account for class imbalances in the results.
- **Confusion Matrix:** A detailed breakdown of correct and incorrect predictions.

This evaluation allowed us to quantify the effectiveness of embedding-based approaches in replicating domain assignments typically performed by human experts.

Model Performance

OpenAI Model (text-embedding-3-small)

The OpenAI model achieved an overall accuracy of **73%**, with strong performance in certain domains such as **Employment Status (F1-score = 1.00)** and **Social Connection (F1-score = 0.97)**. However, some domains, particularly **Medical Cost Burden (F1-score = 0.11)** and **Financial Insecurity (F1-score = 0.50)**, exhibited lower scores due to overlapping boundaries with related concepts such as housing and financial instability (Figure 2).

SentenceTransformer Model (all-MiniLM-L6-v2)

The SentenceTransformer model achieved an overall accuracy of **69%**. Like the OpenAI model, it performed well in the **Employment Status (F1-score = 0.97)** and **Social Connection (F1-score = 0.91)** domains. However, it demonstrated weaker performance in other categories such as **Stress (F1-score = 0.67)** and **Transportation Insecurity (F1-score = 0.57)** (Figure 3).

Figure 2: Performance of OpenAI Embedding Model on Identifying Gravity Project Variables in BDC. Gravity domain annotations from the OpenAI embedding model (text-embedding-3-small) were compared to the manual annotations to judge performance by domain using a confusion matrix (left) and by calculating precision, recall, and F1-Scores (right). Domains with all values of 0.0 had no data points annotated with that domain in either the manual or automated dataset.

Figure 3: Performance of SentenceTransformer Embedding Model on Identifying Gravity Project Variables in BDC. Gravity domain annotations from the SentenceTransformer embedding model (all-MiniLM-L6-v2) were compared to the manual annotations to judge performance by domain using a confusion matrix (left) and by calculating precision, recall, and F1-Scores (right). Domains with all values of 0.0 had no data points annotated with that domain in either the manual or automated dataset.

Comparison of Confusion Matrices and Classification Reports

Both models produced confusion matrices and classification reports revealing varying levels of domain-specific performance. A key observation was the **overlap among related domains** (e.g., housing instability, financial insecurity, and material hardship), which presented challenges for both manual and automated annotation processes.

Key Insights from Evaluation Metrics

The evaluation metrics, including Precision, Recall, and F1-Scores, provided a comprehensive view of the models' performance. Key findings are summarized below:

- **Strengths:** The models excelled in domains with distinct boundaries, such as **Employment Status** and **Social Connection**.
- **Areas for Improvement:** Discrepancies in domains with conceptual overlaps (e.g., **Financial Insecurity** and **Medical Cost Burden**) suggest the need for further refinement of annotation processes and potentially leveraging additional contextual information for classification. In addition, we will calculate Kappa agreement to examine differences in annotator agreement in different domains and value sets.
- **Manual vs. Automated Annotations:** The evaluation demonstrated that embeddings are capable of capturing complex domain relationships but still require human validation for ambiguous or overlapping cases.

Conclusion and Future Work

This research demonstrated the potential of embedding-based methods to automate the annotation and mapping of data within the BDC ecosystem. Leveraging large language models (LLMs) to generate semantic embeddings provides a scalable and efficient solution for mapping variables to standardized domains, reducing manual effort and enhancing data consistency and interoperability. While this effort focused on identification of Gravity Project variables, these embedding-based methods could also be explored to identify other types of variables in large data repositories at scale.

Evaluation of two embedding models, OpenAI's text-embedding-3-small and SentenceTransformer's all-MiniLM-L6-v2, showed strong performance in clearly defined domains, like employment status and social connection. However, overlapping domains like financial insecurity and medical cost burden highlighted challenges requiring further refinement in the annotation process.

Future work will focus on:

1. **Optimal Embedding Model for Maximizing Task Performance:** We will evaluate additional algorithms, such as BERT-based models and custom fine-tuned LLMs, and refine the workflow using active learning and human-in-the-loop feedback to improve annotation precision. Performance metrics will guide the selection of the best embedding model and workflow for the final MVP.
2. **Human Review and Thresholds:** We will define semantic similarity thresholds and establish a human review protocol to ensure accuracy, particularly for low-confidence matches.
3. **Contextual Data to Support Embeddings for Continuous Variables:** While continuous variables provide question and answer value sets for embedding, continuous variables are often represented as questions or variable names only. It is not clear if this

is enough information to create an embedding representation that will result in accurate annotations. We will investigate the adequacy of our current workflow to provide enough contextual information to represent continuous variables in the vector space.

4. **Multi-domain Annotations:** Developing strategies for annotating overlapping domains like housing stability and financial hardship, with expanded vocabularies from sources like AHQR¹⁷ and ScHARe.¹⁸

By addressing these areas, the research aims to enhance the scalability and precision of data annotation within the BDC ecosystem. The outcome will drive improved integration of data across biomedical research, leading to more comprehensive health insights. The long-term goal is an automated, scalable framework for large-scale data mapping to better understand the social factors influencing health outcomes.

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